

summer rice (Feb–May) in 1980 and 1981. No rice varieties grown was found to be resistant. A trial to evaluate six granular insecticides was conducted during 1981 summer.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Pest-susceptible cultivar Suphala (TNI/T141) was transplanted on 21 Feb 1981. Insecticide granules at

1.5 kg ai/ha were broadcast at 15 and 35 d after transplanting, when heavy migratory hopper populations appeared. BPH adult and nymph populations were recorded at 10 and 20 d after treatment (DAT) on a random sample of 10 hills after each application.

Heavy adult population was recorded at 10 DAT, increasing up to

20 DAT with a continuous influx of emigrant hoppers. Hopperburn was noticed with phorate, quinalphos, and disulfoton treatments, resulting in a total yield loss (see table).

The superiority of isoprocarb, carbofuran, and BPMS was evident 10 d after the second treatment, with a significant reduction in nymph population. □

Insect pests of wet season rice in Jabalpur, India

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Wet season rice grown after wheat in Jabalpur is attacked by several insect pests. In a 1984 survey, whitebacked planthopper was a major pest at the vegetative stage, 8–107 hoppers/hill (see table). Rice hispa, although sporadic, was 0.3–12/hill and caused 17–28% damaged leaves.

Rice whorl maggot damage was recorded in this region for the first time during that survey with 5% damaged leaves in early August, increasing to 16%. Populations of rice armyworm started at 0.2 larva/hill and

Insect pests of rice at Jabalpur, India, 1984.

Pest	Economic status ^a	Damage or population ^b
Whitebacked planthopper <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	Major (R)	107 hoppers/hill Jul planting
Rice hispa <i>Dicladisa armigera</i> (Olivier)	Major (S)	12 hispas/hill and 28.3% leaf damage in Jul planting
Rice whorl maggot <i>Hydrellia philippina</i> Ferino	Minor	16% leaf damage in Jul planting
Rice armyworm <i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walker)	Major (R)	1.8 larvae/hill in Jul- Aug planting
Rice green leafhoppers <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	Minor (R)	1–3 hoppers/hill
Yellow stem borer <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walk.)	Minor (R)	1.4% deadhearts
Rice satyrid butterfly <i>Melanitis leda ismene</i> (Cramer)	Minor (S)	Traces
Rice gundhi bug <i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> (Thunberg)	Minor (S)	1–2 bugs/hill

^aR = regular, S = sporadic, ^bPeak population or damage during season.

reached 2 larvae/hill. The 1.3 larvae/hill during the first week of Oct coincided with booting and panicle development. That population was higher than the economic threshold level of 1 larva/hill.

Trace numbers of yellow stem borer, rice skipper *Pelopidus* sp., rice satyrid butterfly, and rice gundhi bug *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunberg) [=varicornis (Fab)] were found. □

Biogas to control rice storage pests

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The major insect pests of stored rice are the Angoumois grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella*, the lesser grain borer *Rhizopertha dominica*, and the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. We tested controlling these pests with biogas from cow dung, consisting of 60% methane, 30–35% carbon dioxide, and traces of other gases.

Effect of biogas on rice storage pests.

Insect	Biogas dose	Time to 10% mortality	
		Without grain	With grain
<i>S. cerealella</i>	20 liters/min	30 s	4 h
<i>S. oryzae</i>	20 liters/min	35 s	4 h 50 min
<i>R. dominica</i>	20 liters/min	50 s	6 h

Twenty-five adults of each pest were placed in 1-kg-capacity closed glass containers and subjected to biogas at 20 liters/min, at 28°C room temperature and 80% relative humidity. Within 30–50 s, all test insects died. No insects died in the untreated check.

Test insects were subjected to 20 liters biogas/min in the presence of 1 kg rough rice. The time to 100% death was 4–6 h (see table). *S. cerealella* was easily killed, followed by *S. oryzae* and finally *R. dominica*. The same treatment also was highly effective in controlling rats. □